

In Practice, a contact group

After three years of activities and in the aftermath of the *Practices in Research* Conference held in October 2021, three successful conferences and three issues of the *Practices in Research* journal (published in 2020, 2021 and 2022), it was decided to make work of broadening the base and academic community of the research group.

In this perspective, an application for a “contact group” was submitted to the FNRS in Belgium (*Fonds National pour la Recherche Scientifique*, Fund for Scientific Research). A contact group, which may be disciplinary or interdisciplinary, and which allows a group of researchers to meet at regular intervals during seminars. The application was successful, meaning that future issues of the journal and the organization of future conferences will be the fruit of a collective reflection by professors, architects, teachers and researchers from ULiège, ULB, UCLouvain, KU Leuven and UAntwerpen.

The aim of the *In Practice* Research Group is to create a link between academic research and professional practice through a forum for exchange and publication accessible to practicing architects, researchers and teachers in architecture. *In Practice* explores different modalities for engaging professional practice in the context of academic research and vice versa. The group aims to encourage architects to conduct academic research based on their project practice and to encourage an exchange platform

between reflexive practitioners (D. Schön, 1984) and academic researchers.

This initiative responds to the paradigm shift in the context of architectural education in Belgium with the integration of higher institutes of architecture into universities since 2013. Where in the higher institutes, the design studio was at the centre of the teaching and the professor-practitioner was the guarantor of his teaching, at the university, the place of research has become increasingly important. This paradigm shift opens up new fields of investigation. *In Practice* makes the meeting of these two modalities of production and transmission of knowledge in architecture (research and practice) effective.

The *In Practice* initiative also responds to the EAAE's Charter on Research in Architecture, which calls for 'a strengthening of the links between theoretical and practical research, and thus between the academic world and the profession'.

The research group aims to go beyond the epistemological debate (FINDELI, 2007, CANDY, 2006, VIAL, 2015, HANROT, 2005) on the issue of research in architecture and instead specifically questions the points of convergence or distinction between professional practice within an agency or other organisation and academic research work.

The *In Practice* contact group will build on the activities that the inter-university research group *In Practice* has developed in recent years: the publication of books on project processes ; the publication of the scientific journal

Practice in Research (double blind peer reviewed) ; and the organisation of conferences and seminars for researchers who integrate their project practice into their research.

Members of the contact group :

Benoit Vandebulcke (President of the contact group, ULiège), Wouter Van Acker (secretary of the contact group, ULB), Éric Le Coguiec (ULiège), Martina Barcelloni Corte (ULiège), Harold Fallon (KU Leuven), Rolf Hughes (KU Leuven), Karen Kesteloot (KU Leuven), Benoit Burquel (ULB), Émilie Morales (ULB), Johan De Walsche (UAntwerpen), Christine Fontaine (UCLouvain), Martin Outers (UCLouvain)

The objective is to further strengthen and precise the research group's epistemological foundations of activities, and to further develop the role of the group as an exchange platform for practicing architects with different research and practice backgrounds.

The editors

Benoît Vandebulcke, Harold Fallon and Benoît Burquel

Bibliography

CANDY L., (2006) *Practice Based Research : A Guide*, CCS Report: 2006-V1.0 November, University of Technology Sydney

FINDELI A., COSTE A., (2007) *De la recherche – création à la recherche - projet : un cadre théorique et méthodologique pour la recherche architecturale*, Lieux Communs n°10, pp.139-161

HANROT S., (2005) *De la recherche à la pratique et vice-versa: le praticien-chercheur*, Proceedings of the colloquium 'The Unthinkable Doctorate' at Sint-Lucas Brussels, p129-139

VIAL S., (2015) *Qu'est-ce que la recherche en design ? Introduction aux sciences du design*, Sciences du design n°1, Presses universitaires de France, p22-36

Practices in Research #03 - Explorations & Cartographies - June 2022

online open access double-blind peer-reviewed journal for practice-based research in architecture.

edited by

Benoît Burquel (ULB); Benoît Vandenbulcke (ULiège); Harold Fallon (KU Leuven)

scientific committee for the conference

Annelies De Smet (KU Leuven), Wouter Van Acker (ULB), Sebastian Kofink (Buero Kofink Schels, Hochschule München), Simon Jüttner (Buero Kofink Schels, Hochschule München), Rolf Hughes (KU Leuven), Lisa De Visscher (A+ Architecture, ULiège), Ido Avissar (List, EAV&T Paris Est), Harold Fallon (AgwA, KU Leuven), Benoît Vandenbulcke (AgwA, ULiège), Benoît Burquel (AgwA, ULB)

scientific committee for the publication

Asli Çiçek (Asli Çiçek, U Hasselt), Caroline Voet (Voet Architectuur, KU Leuven), Karen Kesteloot (Studio Bont, KU Leuven), Bram Aerts (Trans architectuur, stedenbouw, KU Leuven), Claus Peder Pedersen (Arkitektskolen Aarhus), Arnaud Hendrickx (KU Leuven), Nel Janssens (KU Leuven), Johannes Kuehn (Bauhaus Weimar), Xavier Van Rooyen (U Liège), Eric Le Coguic (U Liège)

double-blind peer review process : www.architectureinpractice.eu/pirjournal

front and back cover images : © Maxim Lannaux and Corentin Lefebvre

thanks to Orfée Grandhomme & Ismaël Bennani

Practices in Research is published under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License and fulfils the DOAJ definition of open access. Practices in Research provides immediate Open Access to its content on the principle that making research freely available to the public supports a greater global exchange of knowledge. Copyright for articles published in this journal is retained by the authors without restriction. By appearing in this Open-Access journal, articles are free to use, with proper attribution, in educational and other non-commercial settings.

ISSN: 2736-3996

Practices in Research Journal
Rue des Palais 153 - 1030 Brussels
T. +32 (0)2 244 44 36
info@architectureinpractice.eu
www.architectureinpractice.eu/pirjournal

In Practice

